

High School Mental Health & Academic Pressure Survey

* Indicates required question

1. What grade are you in? *

Mark only one oval.

- Freshman
- Sophomore
- Junior
- Senior

2. What high school do you attend? *

Mark only one oval.

- Neuqua Valley High School
- Waubonsie Valley High School
- Metea Valley High School
- Other: _____

3. What is your gender? *

Mark only one oval.

- Female
- Male
- Non-binary
- Prefer not to say

4. How many AP, honors, or advanced classes are you currently taking? *

Mark only one oval.

- 0
- 1-2
- 3-4
- 5+

5. On average, how many hours of homework do you have each night? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 hour
- 1-2 hours
- 3-4 hours
- 5+ hours
- Other: _____

6. On average, how many hours of studying do you have each night? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 1 hour
- 1-2 hours
- 3-4 hours
- 5+ hours

7. How many extracurriculars (clubs, sports, jobs, etc.) are you involved in? *

Mark only one oval.

- none
- 1
- 2-3
- 4+

8. Do you have a part-time job or work outside of school? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No

9. On a scale of 1–10, how stressed do you feel on a regular school week? *

Mark only one oval.

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10

not : extremely stressed

10. Do you feel like you're constantly behind, even when you're being productive? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes

11. Do you feel guilty when you take breaks or rest? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Sometimes

12. How many hours of sleep do you usually get on a school night? *

Mark only one oval.

- Less than 4
- 4-5 hours
- 6-7 hours
- 8+ hours

13. Do you feel pressure to always be productive, even in your free time? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

14. Where do you feel most of this pressure comes from? *(Select all that apply.)* *

Check all that apply.

- Myself
- Parents
- Teachers/school
- Social Media
- Friends/peers
- Other: _____

15. Has always doing more, staying busy, etc, hurt your mental health? *

Mark only one oval.

- Yes
- No
- Somewhat

16. Do you think high school students are encouraged to value productivity over well-being? *

Mark only one oval.

- Strongly agree
- Agree
- Neutral
- Disagree
- Strongly Disagree

17. What is your race or ethnicity? (Check all that apply.) *

Check all that apply.

- Asian
- Black or African American
- Hispanic or Latino
- Middle Eastern or North African
- Native American or Alaska Native
- Pacific Islander
- White
- Prefer not to say
- Other: _____

18. What helps you manage stress or burnout when it gets overwhelming? (optional)

19. Is there anything you wish schools or adults understood better about student pressure or hustle culture? (optional)

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